

THE INFLUENCE OF FAMILY RELATIONS ON THE PSYCHOLOGY OF CHILDREN AND CONFLICT SITUATIONS

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Abstract: As humanity and society progress, humanity and their relationships to each other also change. Especially in these interpersonal relationships and in the reactions of people to each other in the events taking place in the social environment, in addition to the improvement in the most intimate and close family relationships, sharp changes and many conflict situations are also observed. , such changes and conflicting situations cause damage to family relationships, as well as the psychology of children formed in such situations. Also, there are many shortcomings in the education of such children. Basically, it causes many conflicts between adults and children in the family. In this article, you can get acquainted with the causes of the above-mentioned unpleasant situations and the impact of such situations on the psychology of children, as well as psychological ways and solutions to get out of such conflicting situations.

Key words: Family psychology, conflict situations, child psychology, constructive, destructive, the emotional function of the family.

Introduction: As society progresses, social, psychological, physiological and other changes that occur in people lead to the limitation of the scope of mutual communication relations to a certain extent and the disappearance of the naturalness of relations in them, which in the human psyche ; causing emotional and emotional stress. Such interpersonal relations family life, the law in it is also expressed in rules and universal values.

The socio-economic development of society at a high level has an impact on the formation and improvement of individuals together with cultural and spiritual development. This leads to an increase in demands and wishes placed on each other in interpersonal relations and to a certain degree of thinning of interpersonal relations. I should mention here that we can see such situations not only in social relationships, but also in family relationships. Such situations cause many conflicts in family relationships and cause divorce in many families. A high level of socialization of family adults causes a feeling of resentment

towards each other. If we pay attention to the facts, we can see that the divorce rate of people with higher education is higher than that of people with secondary education. The reason for this, as we mentioned above, is the high demands and wishes of the divorcing persons towards their spouses, and such situations lead to an increase in many conflicting and unpleasant situations between them, and such conflict situations that continue all the time – causes the breakdown of family relations and ultimately leads to family separation. Divorce in the family causes a lot of damage to the society. That is, the main link of society is the family. Family plays an important role in the development of any society. Therefore, divorces in families, together with their influence on the development of the society, cause great harm to the children who are important for the society, who are prone to divorce or who are brought up in single-parent families. Unhealthy environment and relationships in different families and the increase in the number of divorces in families cause several defects in the psychology of children growing up in dysfunctional families. There are many mistakes in the psyche of children brought up or being brought up in such families. The reason for this is, of course, that he was formed in the wrong psychological environment in the family and many mistakes were made in his upbringing. As the child grows up, it constantly leads to a depressive state and difficulties in the process of entering into interpersonal relationships, as well as constant conflict situations in relationships with close people. Divorce in the family causes a lot of damage to the society. That is, the main link of society is the family. Family plays an important role in the development of any society. Therefore, divorces in families, together with their influence on the development of the society, cause great harm to the children who are important for the society, who are prone to divorce or who are brought up in single-parent families. Unhealthy environment and relationships in different families and the increase in the number of divorces in families cause several defects in the psychology of children growing up in dysfunctional families. There are many mistakes in the psyche of children brought up or being brought up in such families. The reason for this is, of course, that he was formed in the wrong psychological environment in the family and many mistakes were made in his upbringing. As the child grows up, it constantly leads to a depressive state and difficulties in the process of entering into interpersonal relationships, as well as constant conflict situations in relationships with close people. You can also see that he behaves inappropriately towards adults. The reason for this is, of course, that they did not get enough of their parents' love during their youth, and

children who grew up seeing their parents talking to each other in an inappropriate way in front of their children, walk with hatred towards adults and a constant mood of resentment and dissatisfaction. is causing him to cry. Such children often show negative reactions to society. And now you can see that such children have qualities such as unkindness and selfishness. Character and main qualities of individuals are formed during adolescence. Adults play an important role in the development and formation of virtues and qualities in children during adolescence. Because children usually learn better what they see. Therefore, parents should be careful about their actions and words in front of their children. Because children quickly learn their every good action and word. Children with such an egoistic character are dangerous for society. Or, most of the children brought up in many dysfunctional and unhealthy families, apart from the affect state, isolate themselves from the society and social environment, seem to protect themselves by covering themselves with a shell and avoid communicating with people. Fearful and indecisive children are formed. . You can also see that he behaves inappropriately towards adults. The reason for this is, of course, that they did not get enough of their parents' love during their youth, and children who grew up seeing their parents talking to each other in an inappropriate way in front of their children, walk with hatred towards adults and a constant mood of resentment and dissatisfaction. is causing him to cry. Such children often show negative reactions to society. And now you can see that such children have qualities such as unkindness and selfishness. Character and main qualities of individuals are formed during adolescence. Adults play an important role in the development and formation of virtues and qualities in children during adolescence. Because children usually learn better what they see. Therefore, parents should be careful about their actions and words in front of their children. Because children quickly learn their every good action and word. Children with such an egoistic character are dangerous for society. Or, most of the children brought up in many dysfunctional and unhealthy families, apart from the affect state, isolate themselves from the society and social environment, seem to protect themselves by covering themselves with a shell and avoid communicating with people. Fearful and indecisive children are formed. . You can also see that he behaves inappropriately towards adults. The reason for this is, of course, that they did not get enough of their parents' love during their youth, and children who grew up seeing their parents talking to each other in an inappropriate way in front of their children, walk with hatred towards adults and a constant mood of

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Therefore, it is necessary to properly form the family, which is considered the main link of society. Before starting a family, we would suggest young people who are on the verge of starting a family to start a family only after they are sufficiently mentally, materially and physically ready for all aspects of family life and attitudes and issues. Only then, the number of divorces in families would decrease, and children's upbringing would be improved. Because, in the family, perfect individuals are raised and matured.

Here, the role of family psychology in reducing and mitigating various conflict situations in the family is invaluable. In this case, the task of family psychology is to prepare young people for family life, together with providing important knowledge about family relations, forming relevant qualifications and skills based on them.

The tasks of family psychology are as follows;

1. Formation of a full-fledged imagination in young people about the role of the family in the formation of personality.
2. To acquaint young people in a scientific way about the socio-historical origin of the family and the unpleasant and incomprehensible situations in family relations that may arise in the family.
3. To give young people a scientifically based full-fledged idea about the changes, problems, and laws that occur in family life and to prepare them in a suitable manner for such events.
4. To teach young people to give a constructive tone to the problems that arise in family life, to avoid destructive directions.

5. To teach young people reasonable ways to get out of family relations and problematic situations in life (in a way that does not negatively affect the stability of the family and the psyche of children being raised in the family).

6. Formation of skills in choosing the right spouse in young people.

7. Preparing young people for family communication.

8. It consists in forming knowledge and skills that increase the strength of the family in young people.

The above recommendations will help prevent problems and conflicts in the family. A conflict is a clash of opposing views, positions, and goals, and such situations mainly occur in the process of communication. Conflict situations in the family arise due to differences in views between the elders of the family, that is, the spouses. And usually, when such a situation occurs, it is better to try to get out of such a situation rationally, because such seemingly insignificant conflict situations can lead to the breakdown of the family. First of all, you should try to be as far away from the things that cause such situations as possible, and try to solve the things that need to be discussed or resolved through constructive and calm communication.

The strength of the family and the proper upbringing of children in the family, the emotional and emotional function of the family - building warm relationships between each member of the family in the family, kindness, care, support for each other and it means showing qualities such as treating each other with respect. In this, the elders of the family should be a good example to the younger ones. Only then, the spiritual and psychological environment of the family will be healthy.

In conclusion, the children in the family should not be harmed due to the different wishes and desires of the adult. We must be careful in raising children and communicating with them, and we must form mature and strong willed and truly patriotic individuals for society.

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